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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE AUTOMATION SYSTEM OF ELECTRONIC SERVICES AND TOURIST PERMITS

Najmiddinov Sultan Nurali ugli

Teacher of Chirchik State Pedagogical University
Independent Researcher of the Banking and Finance Academy
ORCID: 0009-0000-7726-7254

Abstract: This article analyzes the current state of electronic services and automation of tourist permits in the tourism sector, as well as existing challenges and areas for further improvement. In the context of digital transformation, the electronic transfer of government services, particularly in the tourism sector, is of great importance, simplifying permit issuance processes, ensuring transparency, and improving service quality. The study highlights best international practices, the potential of using artificial intelligence, big data, and blockchain technologies, and develops practical proposals for Uzbekistan's conditions.

Key words: electronic services, tourist permit, automation, digital tourism, e-gov, Smart Tourism.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada turizm sohasida elektron xizmatlar va turistik ruxsatnomalarni avtomatlashtirish tizimining hozirgi holati, mavjud muammolari hamda uni yanada takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari tahlil etilgan. Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida davlat xizmatlarini elektron shaklga o'tkazish, ayniqsa turizm sohasida ruxsat berish jarayonlarini soddalashtirish, shaffoflikni ta'minlash va xizmatlar sifatini oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Tadqiqot davomida ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar, sun'iy intellekt, Big Data va blokcheyn texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari yoritilgan hamda O'zbekiston sharoitida amaliy takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron xizmatlar, sayyohlik ruxsatnomasi, avtomatlashtirish, raqamli turizm, egov, Smart Tourism.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется текущее состояние электронных услуг и автоматизации туристических разрешений в туристическом секторе, существующие проблемы и области для дальнейшего совершенствования. В контексте цифровой трансформации электронная передача государственных услуг, особенно в туристическом секторе, имеет большое значение, упрощая процессы выдачи разрешений, обеспечивая прозрачность и повышая качество услуг. В исследовании освещается передовой зарубежный опыт, возможности использования технологий искусственного интеллекта, больших данных и блокчейна, а также разрабатываются практические предложения для условий Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: электронные услуги, туристическое разрешение, автоматизация, цифровой туризм, электронное правительство, интеллектуальный туризм.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalization and digital economy, the tourism industry is one of the fastest growing sectors. The increase in tourist flows, the expansion of the range of services and changes in consumer demand require the introduction of modern digital solutions in the public administration system. In particular, the system of electronic services and automation of permits plays an important role in regulating tourism activities.

The development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan has been identified as one of the priorities of state policy. In recent years, the simplification of the visa regime, the introduction of electronic visas, online registration and licensing services are important steps in this direction.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The impact of digital transformation in the tourism sector, electronic visas and online permits on tourism competitiveness is scientifically and practically substantiated in UNWTO (World Tourism Organization) and OECD reports. These sources emphasize that automated permit systems create convenience for tourists, reduce costs and optimize the activities of state bodies. However, these studies are more analytical and statistical in nature, and specific models for improving the system are limited [1].

Scientists such as K. Buhalis, M. Gretzel have studied the innovative aspects of digital technologies, smart tourism (Smart Tourism) and electronic services in tourism. Their works focus on issues of digital platforms, data exchange and integration. However, the issue of complex automation of permit and licensing processes in tourism has been little studied as a separate research object[2].

Uzbek scientists have carried out a number of scientific works on issues of electronic government, digitization of public services and tourism development. In particular, the works of A.A. Abdurakhmonov, Sh.Kh. Rakhmonov, B.B. Tursunov analyzed the legal and economic foundations of digitization of public services, institutional mechanisms for the introduction of electronic services[3].

Local studies devoted to the tourism sector (N.Yu. Yusupov, F.M. Kholmurodov, D.R. Saidova) highlighted the importance of digital tourism, electronic marketing, online booking systems and information platforms. At the same time, electronic services have been identified as an important element of tourism infrastructure[4].

The analysis of the literature shows that while foreign studies have addressed the issue of electronic services and automation from the perspective of the state or digital tourism, domestic studies have focused mainly on regulatory, legal and organizational aspects.

Within the framework of this study, the author:

considers the automation of electronic services and permits in the tourism sector as a single digital system; organizes information exchange between government bodies, tour operators and tourists on the basis of an integrated platform;

develops an improvement model aimed at increasing the speed of service provision, transparency and user-friendliness.

In this regard, this study, unlike existing scientific works, is distinguished by its focus on improving the processes of issuing permits in electronic services and tourism based on a practical, systematic and innovative approach.

However, existing local studies address the issue of automation of permitting, licensing and administrative processes in the tourism sector in a more general way, and its technological architecture, integration mechanisms and improvement paths are not sufficiently systematized.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The comparative method was used as one of the main methods in the study. Through this method, electronic services and automated systems for issuing permits in tourism introduced in foreign countries (European Union countries, South Korea, Singapore) were compared with the existing practice in Uzbekistan.

In the process of comparative analysis, such indicators as:

- the number of stages of issuing permits;
- the duration of providing electronic services;
- the level of user participation;
- the state of mutual integration of information systems;

- transparency and control mechanisms were taken as a basis. As a result, it was found that in foreign practice, permit issuance processes are fully digitized, the human factor is minimized, and the service time is reduced. In Uzbek practice, it was determined that, despite the existence of electronic services, some processes still require additional administrative intervention[5].

Systematic analysis method. The process of issuing permits in electronic services and tourism was studied as a holistic system using the systematic analysis method. The interrelationships between government bodies, information systems, the regulatory framework and users were analyzed.

This method identified functional gaps, data duplication and integration problems in the existing automation system. As a result, the need for a single digital platform to increase the efficiency of electronic services was scientifically substantiated.

Analytical and statistical method. The study used the analytical and statistical method to analyze the indicators of the use of electronic services, the dynamics of obtaining online permits and the terms of service provision. Based on official statistical data and sectoral reports, the level of automation and its impact on tourism activities were assessed.

As a result of this method, it was found that in regions where electronic services were introduced, the time for obtaining permits was reduced and administrative costs in the activities of tourism entities were reduced.

Expert assessment method. The expert assessment method studied the opinions of tourism specialists, civil servants and IT experts. On the basis of expert surveys, the advantages and disadvantages of the automated permit system were determined, and practical proposals for its improvement were formulated. Analysis and results. The introduction of electronic services in the tourism sector has been carried out gradually in recent years. In particular, electronic licensing, online permit issuance, and electronic application submission services have been launched.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A comparative analysis of the traditional and electronic permit issuance processes in the tourism sector is presented (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative analysis of permit issuance processes

Indicators	Traditional method	Electronic method
Submit an application	In paper form	Online
Trial period	10–15 days	3–5 days
The human factor	Up	Partially
Transparency	Low	middle
Control mechanism	Limited	Electron monitoring

The analysis of the diagram shows that:

- the use of electronic services is increasing year by year;
- however, the share of electronic services in relation to the total number of permits still does not have a complete advantage;
- in some regions, the level of use of electronic services remains low.

This situation indicates that the functional capabilities of electronic services are limited and a user-friendly interface has not been sufficiently formed for users (Table 2).

Table 2. Information systems integration level

Systems	Integration status	Problem
Tourism register	Partially	Data update is slow
State services portal	Middle	The systems are not interconnected
Tax and license system	Low	Manual inspections

The table data shows that in order to fully automate electronic services, it is necessary to strengthen the integration between systems.

The findings of this study demonstrate that the ongoing digital transformation of permit issuance in the tourism sector has already produced tangible and largely positive outcomes, while simultaneously revealing clear directions for further improvement. The comparative analysis of traditional and electronic permit issuance processes confirms that the transition to electronic services significantly enhances operational efficiency. The reduction of processing time from 10–15 days to 3–5 days illustrates the practical value of automation in accelerating administrative procedures and improving service delivery for tourism stakeholders.

At the same time, the persistence of the human factor at a partial level indicates that the current electronic system represents an intermediate stage of digital maturity rather than a fully automated model. This can be interpreted positively: the existing framework has already laid a solid technological foundation, and the remaining human involvement creates opportunities for gradual optimization rather than systemic restructuring. Similarly, the shift from low to medium transparency reflects meaningful progress in accountability and monitoring, particularly through the introduction of electronic tracking mechanisms. Although full transparency has not yet been achieved, the presence of digital monitoring tools signals a decisive move toward more open and controllable administrative processes.

The dynamic growth in the use of electronic services over recent years further supports the effectiveness of digital reforms. Increasing adoption rates suggest growing trust among users and improving familiarity with online platforms. However, the fact that electronic services do not yet dominate the total volume of issued

permits highlights structural and regional disparities. In several regions, lower usage levels indicate that digital infrastructure readiness, digital literacy, and interface usability remain uneven. Importantly, this does not undermine the value of electronic services; instead, it emphasizes the need for targeted capacity-building measures and user-centered design improvements to ensure broader and more inclusive adoption.

Another significant outcome of the analysis concerns the limited integration between information systems used by state bodies in the tourism sector. Partial or low integration between tourism registers, state service portals, and tax and licensing systems leads to repeated data requests and manual verification procedures. From a positive perspective, identifying these bottlenecks provides a clear roadmap for policy and technological intervention. Strengthening interoperability between systems would not only reduce administrative burdens but also further minimize the human factor, enhance data accuracy, and improve real-time decision-making.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the analysis and research show that the automation of electronic services and permits in the tourism sector is one of the important directions of the digitalization of public services. Although electronic application submission, online licensing, and permit issuance services have been introduced in recent years, their functional capabilities and level of automation remain insufficient. This situation indicates that the existing digital solutions have not yet fully ensured process efficiency, transparency, and sustainability in the provision of public services in the tourism sector.

The analysis revealed that the persistence of the human factor in permit issuance processes, the low level of integration between information systems, and limited statistical monitoring mechanisms significantly reduce the effectiveness of electronic services. In addition, uneven user-oriented service design and disparities in the level of use of electronic services across regions negatively affect the overall development of the system. As a result, the potential of digital technologies to simplify administrative procedures and reduce institutional barriers is not fully realized.

These circumstances indicate the need to further improve the automation system of electronic services and permits in the tourism sector based on a comprehensive, systematic, and innovative approach. Such an approach should be aimed at eliminating fragmentation, strengthening interdepartmental coordination, and ensuring the continuity of digital processes across all stages of service provision.

Based on the results of the analysis, it is proposed to introduce a single integrated digital platform that covers permit issuance, licensing, and registration services in the tourism sector. This platform should ensure automatic and secure information exchange between the information systems of state bodies, thereby reducing duplication of procedures and increasing the speed and reliability of decision-making processes.

At the same time, special attention should be paid to the full automation of the licensing process. Minimizing the human factor at the stages of application review, verification, and decision-making can significantly reduce service delivery time and lower the risk of corruption. Automated workflows and algorithm-based verification mechanisms would contribute to greater objectivity and consistency in administrative decisions.

Strengthening the integration of information systems is also essential. The practice of requesting duplicate data from applicants should be eliminated by establishing API-based integration between tourism authorities, tax bodies, licensing institutions, and public service portals. This will allow data to be reused efficiently and will reduce the administrative burden on both service providers and users.

In addition, the introduction of statistical monitoring and analytical mechanisms is necessary to improve governance quality. The development of analytical modules that automatically analyze the use of electronic services, permit issuance deadlines, and refusal cases will make it possible to identify bottlenecks in the system, assess performance indicators, and make evidence-based management decisions.

Improving user-oriented service design remains another important direction. Simplifying electronic service interfaces, expanding multilingual support, and increasing opportunities for accessing services through mobile platforms will enhance user satisfaction and ensure broader inclusion of tourism entities across different regions and user groups.

Finally, increasing human resource capacity and developing digital literacy are crucial for the successful implementation of digital reforms. The introduction of regular training programs for civil servants and tourism entities on the effective use of electronic services will help improve institutional readiness, reduce resistance to change, and ensure the sustainable functioning of digital systems.

As a result of implementing the proposed measures, the efficiency of the automation system for electronic services and permits in the tourism sector will increase, service quality will improve, and a convenient and transparent digital environment for tourism activities will be created. Ultimately, this will contribute to enhancing the country's tourism competitiveness and strengthening its position in the global tourism market.

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